

Griffith standard integrated motion capture data collection protocol

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1 Booking an appointment

Preparing for the motion capture session will often commence a number of weeks before the motion capture as there are several important tasks that need to be completed once the participant has been recruited so that the session runs smoothly.

Ask the participant their shoe size

Ask the participant to wear appropriate clothing

Book the laboratory

Check stock of consumables for session

Set reminder to charge EMGs

Arrange lab staff

1.1 Standard shoes for testing

This protocol uses standard shoes (i.e., Dunlop Volley) during testing. When booking the appointment, ask participants their shoe size and check that a pair of shoes is available in that size. If the required size is unavailable, inform the laboratory manager as early as possible before the session so a pair can be purchased or alternative arrangements can be made. Reschedule the session as required.

1.2 Clothing

Participants should be asked to wear clothing appropriate for motion analysis. This means clothing that allows passive reflective markers (PRMs) and electromyography (EMG) sensors to be placed on the skin, especially around the hip, pelvis and upper thigh, is essential. Suitable clothing for men include sports shorts or swimming costumes and a t-shirt or singlet top. Suitable clothing for women includes sports shorts and exercise tops. Trousers, leggings, yoga pants or long shorts are not appropriate.

1.3 Book the laboratory

Book the laboratory using the shared calendar through the Griffith webmail client. If you do not have access to the laboratory calendar, ask the laboratory manager to grant you access or to make the booking on your behalf.

1.4 Consumables

At the time of booking the appointment, check the inventory of consumables for materials required for testing:

- Double sided tape
- Coban/Medichill/Surgifix
- Micropore
- Sports tape

- Razors
- Abrasion pads
- Alcohol swabs
- EMG electrodes (Duotrodes, Ag/AgCl)

Make arrangements to purchase gait lab consumables during the early stages of project planning. Space is available to store consumables for specific projects in the integrated **Motion Analysis Laboratory (iMAL)** at Griffith University (G02 0.01). If you run out of consumables during a project, make arrangements to purchase them through the laboratory manager or technical services. Do not use other researchers' supplies, unless approved by them.

1.5 EMG charge reminder

Set a reminder to charge the EMG sensors fully the night before the test. The sensors are fully charged after 7 hours. Note that to maintain battery life, EMG sensors should not be charged for more than 7 hours. There are timed power outlets available in the lab that you can use to set the start time so that charging is complete before testing commences.

1.6 Laboratory staff

The musculoskeletal research group promotes professional conduct of these data capture activities and two researchers must be present to collect the data at all times. During motion capture, one staff member will operate Vicon, while the other should be in position to confirm force plate strikes.

Both staff members should be familiar with the procedures in this manual and will be responsible for preparing the lab and collecting high quality data. If the participant is female then it is preferable that one lab staff member should also be female.

1.7 Overview of testing

- Prepare the laboratory
- Prepare the subject (anthropometric measurements and EMG)
- Strength testing
- Motion capture marker placement
- Motion capture
- Clean up

2 Preparing the laboratory

Assemble required equipment
Power up system (Vicon, workstation and amplifiers)
Check appropriate coverage of the capture volume
Calibrate Vicon system
Check acquisition rates
Check force plates

The following instructions assume that you are using the integrated **Motion Analysis Laboratory** (iMAL) at Griffith University (G02 0.01). iMAL (Figure 2.1)

Figure 2.1: Schematic of the integrated **Motion Analysis Laboratory** (iMAL).

2.1 Power-up system

Turn on the main workstation, Vicon Giganets and force plate amplifiers. It is best practice to give the system 30 minutes to warm up and achieve a stable temperature. Try to keep the temperature in the lab constant, changes in temperature will affect the lenses in the cameras and affect reconstruction of the trajectories. This can be handled in post processing by manipulating the environmental drift tolerance. While you are waiting for the system to come to temperature, you can prepare the passive reflective markers (PRMs) and EMG sensors (sections 2.2 and 2.3) for the capture.

2.2 Assemble equipment

The data collection sheet includes a checklist of equipment that is required for motion capture. Assemble all required equipment onto the mobile Mayo stand or cart.

There are 93 markers in the standard Griffith marker set and 109 markers in the expanded Griffith marker set. To form these marker sets requires 73 individual markers and up to 12 three-marker clusters. These should be prepared by affixing double sided tape to the clusters and marker pedestals. Handle the reflective surfaces of the markers minimally with your fingers, over time the acid reduces retro-reflective quality.

Prepare 16 EMG sensors taking into account the charging and assembly guidelines specific to the system being used in section 2.3. You need to apply double sided tape to rear of the sensors and have 16 electrodes, plus some spares, and razors and skin swabs at hand.

2.3 EMG sensors

2.3.1 Cometa Wave wireless EMG

If you are using the Cometa EMG sensors, combine a battery unit with the transmitter cover (Figure 2.2). Slide the sensor onto the battery unit, check that both slide tabs, on either side of the transmitter cover, fit into the runner without any resistance. If you have trouble getting the cover to fit, pick another battery unit. Do not force the cover onto a battery unit. Check that the EMG wireless receiver shows a green light corresponding to the cover number. This confirms a connection between the EMG sensor and the workstation. If the light is not green, try another battery unit for that cover. Clip the button press studs onto the EMG electrodes.

Figure 2.2: The Cometa Wave wireless EMG sensor showing the transmitter cover and battery unit and assembly.

2.3.2 Noraxon

If you're using the Noraxon EMG sensors, remove them from the charging station and verify the leads are firmly connected to the sensors. The sensor's light should be blinking green. Sensors automatically turn off after not being used for a long period (not a problem during data collection). If sensors are off, place them back in their charging station to wake them up.

Figure 2.3: The Noraxon Wireless EMG sensor. The leads separate and must be firmly attached to the sensors.

2.4 Vicon set up

- 👍 Check coverage
- 👍 Clear camera masks
- 👍 Check for and remove reflections
- 👍 Mask cameras
- 👍 Calibrate cameras (error 0.02 or less)
- 👍 Set volume origin
- 👍 Prepare enough passive reflective markers for Griffith marker set

After allowing the system to warm up, open Vicon Nexus on the workstation. In the resources pane of Vicon Nexus click 'Go Live'. On the system tab in the resources pane Load the system configuration "GriffithStandard" from the drop down menu. Check acquisition rates for the analog and video capture. The analog capture should be 2000 Hz. The video capture should be 200 Hz. Then, go to the system preparation tab of the tools pane (Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.4: Vicon Nexus GUI showing 1. the calibration setup tab in the tools pane; 2. The system pane with hardware inputs; 3. the view drop down menu.

Start by checking coverage of the cameras. Place the calibration wand or several markers on the main force plate in the capture volume. You may also like to put some markers on the floor designating the desired capture volume so that you can be sure that you are acquiring everything that you need. Select 'camera view' from the view drop down menu and then select the cameras from the System pane (Figure 2.4). Click 'Clear the mask from the camera'. You should be able to see the markers in the 3D perspective view. Check individual cameras. Check that all cameras can see the markers and that the markers are located in the bottom of the field of view of the camera. Inspect the camera view for any reflections and locate these in the lab space and remove them or put some tape over them if it is possible to do so. The strobes from other cameras recording the volume will show up in camera view, ignore these for the moment. If it is not clear what object in the field of view is object creating the reflection and especially if the reflection is 'flashing' or 'blinking', as a last resort, adjust the camera threshold until the reflection disappears from the camera image. The threshold value should generally be in the range of 0.2 to 0.4 units.

Once your cameras are aimed at the capture volume and you have checked for reflections, remove any additional markers you placed in the capture volume leaving the wand on the force plate. Orient the cameras by clicking set volume origin. you can use either the 5 marker or active wand for this but make sure that you set the wand type to match what you're using in the 'Advanced settings'. Place the wand with the long edge running between plates one and two and the short edge running between plate two and four (Figure 2.5). When placed, make sure that the wand is level using the spirit level incorporated into the wand. Click 'set volume origin'. Remove the wand from the force plates and mask the cameras. Click 'Start' under 'Mask Cameras' on the system preparation tab. Alternatively, you can place masks on the camera manually to minimise the amount of masking.

Finally, calibrate the capture volume. You can use the 5 marker wand or active wand for this, but make sure that you set the wand type in the advanced settings to match what you're using. Click 'calibrate cameras'. The number of frames can be selected in the calibration pane and should be no less than

2000 frames. The LED on the front of the cameras will begin to flash blue. Stand in the centre of the capture volume, over the plates and wave the wand in a circular motion. Make sure that you focus on the all the areas at the centre of the capture volume, above the force plates, but also at least one metre either end of the force plates. Calibration will end when all camera have required number of frames (LEDs on cameras will be green). Calibration is satisfactory if the error number for all cameras is 0.02 or less. If one or two cameras are greater than this value, select the cameras from the System pane, select 'selected cameras' from the 'Cameras to Calibrate' drop down menu under 'Advanced settings' and then click 'Start' again.

2.5 Force plate set up

- 👍 Check vertical GRF measure
- 👍 Check force vector location

Four (4) AMTI force plates can be housed in 9 force plate positions in the iMAL (Figure 2.5). Currently, there are force plates in position 1, 2, 5 and 8. Before the capture, the force output and vector location from the force plates need to be checked. To check the force output, place the 10 kg dumbbell weight IN THE MIDDLE of the force plate. In Vicon, check the vertical GRF measured by the force plate matches the expected weight (98.1 N). If not, remove the weight, zero the force plate and then re-test.

Figure 2.5: Location and orientation of the calibration wand for setting the volume origin.

Test that the force plate is configured correctly by checking the visualisation of the force plate vector in the 3D perspective view (Figure 2.6). Move the 10 kg dumbbell weight from the middle to the edge of force plate. Confirm that the force vector shown in the 3D perspective corresponds to the position

of the dumbbell weight. As a further check, walk over the plates and make sure that the force vector and centre of pressure visualise in the direction of motion.

Repeat for other force plates used in your system configuration.

Figure 2.6: Checking force plate vectors by comparing the magnitude and location of the force vector using the weight (A and B) and visualisation of the point of application of the force vector during a walk (C and D).

2.6 Create subject and session in Vicron Nexus:

Create a new session for the capture

- Select “Baseline” (data management)
- Go to “Subject Tab” on Nexus Resource pane
- NEW Subject: click the icon for “Create a new subject from a template”

- Select the labelling template (VST file) “GU10 mkrClus” or “GU6mkrClus”
- Enter participant ID in popup dialog box, e.g. M01
- Click the participant ID to see their Subject Measurements (fill in all necessary measures: leg length, knee width, height, mass, etc.)
- Set session as either Session_1 or Session 2 for baseline or various follow-up timepoints or in the format YYYYMMDD

2.7 Set up Biodex

Make sure that the BIODEX power supply is turned on (rear of unit) and turn on the Biodex computer (in trolley cabinet under monitor). The BIODEX will start and prompt to initialise the dynamometer controller (Figure 2.7). Make sure that there are no attachments connected to the dynamometer moment arm (Figure 4.1). Click ‘OK’ to initialise the dynamometer controller. The dynamometer will start the initialisation process, moving for about 2-3 minutes.

Figure 2.7: Prompt to initialise the dynamometer controller. Make sure that there are no attachments connected and click ‘OK’ to continue.

Start the LabView software, the front panel will open (Figure 2.8). Click ‘run’ (the play button).

Figure 2.8: The LabView software set up panel. Click on the play button (red circle) to continue.

2.8 Final check

Before the participant arrives do a final check. Make sure you have:

- The consent form
- Calibrated Vicon
- Sufficient consumables:
 - Coban
 - Sports tape
 - Micropore
 - EMG electrodes (double the amount needed)
 - Razors
 - Abrasive pads
 - Alcohol swabs
- Assembled EMG sensors and signals are being received
- Taped all PRMs and EMG sensors with double sided tape
- Initialised Biodex

3 Preparing the participant

Informed consent

Anthropometric measurements

EMG sensor placement

3.1 Welcome and consent

Welcome the participant, briefly explain the structure and procedures of the session using text similar to the following:

“We are going to attach these markers and ask you to walk through the space between the cameras. The cameras will record the movements of the markers and from that we can calculate your joint angles and range of motion. We will also collect information about which muscles are contracting using EMG sensors like this one. The tests should take only around an hour, but we have 2 hours of preparation to get you ready.

First, I’m going to ask you to read this information sheet about today’s motion capture. I’ll answer any questions that you have after you read the information. If you’re happy to go ahead then I’ll ask you to sign the consent sheet to participate. If you agree to go ahead with the motion capture today but find later that you don’t want to continue for any reason you can pull out at any time”.

Answer any questions that the participant has and collect the signed consent form from them.

3.2 Anthropometry

- 👍 Height and weight
- 👍 Segment and foot lengths
- 👍 Anatomic angles

It is important to collect the following anthropometric measurements

3.2.1 Height and weight

To measure height, ask the participant to stand with their back to the stadiometer/wall in a neutral posture with their heels together, weight distributed evenly on both feet and head positioned so that the line of vision is perpendicular to the body. Ask the participant to stand with their feet together and looking straight ahead. Ask the participant to inhale deeply and hold the position. The movable headboard is brought onto the topmost point on the head with sufficient pressure to compress the hair. Record the height to the nearest 0.1 mm.

Measure weight using the scales and with the participant barefoot.

3.2.2 Inter-ASIS distance

With the participant standing during height and weight measurements or laying supine during EMG sensor placement, palpate and mark the ASIS. Measure the distance using a tape measure.

3.2.3 Leg length

With the participant either standing during height and weight measurements, or laying supine during EMG sensor placement, palpate and mark the ASIS and the lateral malleolus on the same side of the body. Measure the distance using a tape measure. Repeat for the other side.

3.2.4 Foot length

Measure the foot from the heel to the Hallux. Measure the foot from the heel to the tip of the longest toe. Repeat for the other side.

3.2.5 Eversion angle

With the participant supine, mark the tibial tuberosity and the middle of the anterior ankle joint space. Align one arm of the goniometer along the line formed by these two marks, which should correspond with the lateral edge of the tibia. With the fulcrum of the goniometer between the malleoli, move the foot to maximum eversion and line the distal arm of the goniometer up with the second metatarsal. Take the reading of the angle from the circular disc.

3.3 Electromyography

- 👉 Mark the electrode position
- 👉 Prepare the skin
- 👉 Place the electrode
- 👉 Test the quality of the EMG signal
- 👉 Complete MVIC and dynamometry
- 👉 Reinforce with coband prior to commencing dynamic tasks

3.3.1 Electrode placement

EMG data are collected for 16 muscles. The locations for electrode placement are listed in Table 3.1.

Using the location guide in Table 3.1, palpate bony landmarks and determine the ideal position for the electrode on the participant. Mark a line between the landmarks using the eyeliner pencil. Then cross the line with another line corresponding to the orientation of the electrode to create an X.

If you are using grounded sensors (e.g. Noraxon) the sensor should ideally be placed on a bony landmark or, at the very least, not placed on the same muscle being recorded.

Some bony landmarks are close to the genital region (i.e., the ischial tuberosity). It is important that both research staff are present for identification of landmarks for sensor placement in these areas. Remember to keep the participant informed of what you are doing by telling them which landmark you are targeting. With palpation of landmarks around the genital region, tell the participant what you would like to do and ask them if it is OK. If they are uncomfortable, it is sufficient for you to describe the landmark again e.g., "I am looking for the ischial tuberosity, that is the bone at the bottom of the pelvis that you sit on" and ask them to palpate themselves and point to the bone.

For each muscle, locate the position for electrode placement and then complete skin preparation (section 3.3.2) before placing the electrode.

Vicon channel number	Muscle & OpenSim label [ref]	Sensor placement		Palpation	Sensor orientation
1	<i>Vastus medialis</i> (<i>vasmed</i>) [1]	At 80% of line between ASIS & knee joint space at anterior border of medial ligament		Seated & resisted knee extension, hip & knee at 90°	Perpendicular to line between ASIS & knee joint space at anterior border of medial ligament
2	<i>Vastus lateralis</i> (<i>vaslat</i>) [1]	At 2/3 of line from ASIS to lateral aspect of patella		Seated & resisted knee extension, hip & knee at 90°	In the direction of muscle fibres
3	<i>Rectus femoris</i> (<i>recfem</i>) [1]	Midpoint of line between ASIS & superior aspect of patella		Seated & resisted hip flexion, hip & knee at 90°	In the direction of line from ASIS to the superior aspect of patella
4	Gracilis (<i>gra</i>) [4]	Midpoint between pubic tubercle & medial femoral condyle		Supine, hip flexed to 45°, knee flexed at 90°	In the direction of muscle fibres
5	Sartorius (<i>sar</i>) [2]	4cm distal from ASIS (stay proximal to minimize cross talk with Rec fem)		Hip flexion in supine (or standing), knee at 45°, with external femoral rotation	In the direction of muscle fibres

Vicon channel number	Muscle & OpenSim label [ref]	Sensor placement		Palpation	Sensor orientation
6	Tibialis anterior (tibant) [1]	At 1/3 on the line between the tip of fibula & the tip of medial malleolus (prox.)		Support the leg above the ankle joint with the ankle joint in dorsiflexion & foot in inversion.	In the direction of line between the tip of fibula & tip of medial malleolus.
7	Peroneus longus (perlong) [1]	At ¼ of line between the tip of head of fibula to the tip of lateral malleolus		Support leg above ankle. Evert foot in plantar flexion, apply pressure against lateral border & sole of foot in direction of inversion & dorsiflexion.	In the direction of line between the tip of head of fibula to the tip of lateral malleolus.
8	Adductor group (addgrp) [2]	Palpate the tendon arising from pubic tubercle & place the electrode four fingerbreadths distal to pubic tubercle over muscle belly.		While seated, resist adduction	Perpendicular to the line between the Superior pubic ramus/ischiu m and the medial femoral condyle
9	Med Hams (semimem) [1]	Midway between ischial tuberosity & medial tib condyle		Hip extension & knee flexion in prone, knee at 45°, with internal tibial rotation	In the direction of line between the ischial tuberosity & the medial epicondyle of tibia
10	Lat Hams (bicfemlh) [1]	Midway between ischial tuberosity & lateral tib condyle		Thigh extension & knee flexion in prone, knee at 45°, with external tibial rotation	In the direction of line between the ischial tuberosity & the lateral epicondyle of tibia

Vicon channel number	Muscle & OpenSim label [ref]	Sensor placement		Palpation	Sensor orientation
11	Medial Gastroc. (gasmed) [1]	Over area of greatest muscle bulk (\approx 30% med tib condyle)		Resisted ankle plantar flexion while prone with knee slightly flexed	Parallel with line connecting the triceps surae aponeurosis & the middle of medial femoral condyle
12	Lateral Gastroc. (gaslat) [1]	At 1/3 of line between head of fibula & heel		Resisted ankle plantar flexion while prone with knee slightly flexed	In the direction of line between the head of fibula & the heel
13	Soleus (sol) [1]	At 2/3 of line between the medial condylis of femur & medial malleolus (distal)		Resisted ankle plantar flexion while prone with knee slightly flexed	In the direction of line between the medial condylis to the medial malleolus
14	Tensor fasciae latae (tfl) [1]	At 1/6 line from ASIS to lateral femoral condyle (proximal)		Hip abduction while lying on the contralateral side	In the direction of line from the anterior spina iliaca superior to the lateral femoral condyle.
15	Gluteus medius (glutmed) [1]	At 1/2 of line from the crista iliaca to the trochanter		Hip abduction with manual resistance	In the direction of line from the crista iliaca to the trochanter

Vicon channel number	Muscle & OpenSim label [ref]	Sensor placement		Palpation	Sensor orientation
16	Gluteus maximus (glutmax) [1]	At ½ of line between the sacral vertebrae & greater trochanter		Hip extension in prone with external femoral rotation	In direction of line from PSIS to the middle of posterior aspect of thigh

Table 3.1: EMG placements for Griffith standard motion capture protocol

3.3.2 Skin preparation

The skin must be prepared to ensure good electrode-skin contact. Good electrode-skin contact is critical for high quality surface EMG-recordings; it reduces skin impedance, artefacts (electrical interference) and electrode imbalance (smaller common mode disturbance signal) and improves the signal to noise ratio.

The skin preparation process is:

- i) Use a new razor to shave the area gently to remove the hair
- ii) Rub the skin gently with an abrasive pad to remove dead skin cells
- iii) Wipe the area with an alcohol swab to remove any oil, moving in a direction away from the site to avoid contamination

Remember to keep the participant informed of what you are doing at each step.

3.3.3 Check the signal

Once an electrode has been placed, check the signal using the movement listed in Table 3.1. If the signal is satisfactory (i.e. there is a signal when the muscle is contracting and there is minimal cross talk during a static contraction), remove the backing from the double sided tape, place the sensor on the skin and proceed to the next muscle. If not, check the position again using the sensor placement instructions in Table 3.1.

3.4 Maximal voluntary isometric contractions

Acquire maximal voluntary isometric contractions (MVIC) for normalisation of EMG data. The MVICs consist of manually resisted, jumping and isometric strength tasks.

3.4.1 Manually resisted MVIC

Three (3) manually resisted tasks are to be performed. For these tasks the participant should be seated in chair, with feet flat on the ground and knees at 90°. Instructions and locations for manual resistance are provided in Table 3.2.

Test	Ask the participant to...	Resistance	Number of repetitions	Trial name
Ankle Dorsiflexion	Lift their foot off the ground (dorsi flexion)	Oppose dorsi flexion by applying resistance to the dorsal surface of the foot	2	(_Dorsiflexion)
Ankle Eversion	'Roll' ankle inwards to lift their little toe off the ground (eversion)	Oppose eversion by applying resistance to the dorsal and lateral surface of the foot	2	(_Eversion)
Sartorius	With the knee at 90°, Externally rotate the thigh into the 'tailors' position	Oppose external rotation of the thigh by applying resistance to the medial ankle	2	(_Sartorius)

Table 3.2: Manually resisted MVIC tasks.

3.4.2 Jumps

Acquire two (2) jumping tasks, a counter movement jump for lower limb muscles and a jump with the knees locked for plantar flexors (Table 3.3). For both tasks, the participant should be standing with one foot on force plate 1 and one foot on force plate 2.

Test	Ask the participant to...	Number of repetitions	Trial name
Vertical Jump (Counter movement jump)	From a standing position, perform a CMJ, i.e. bend your knees and then jump as high as possible	2	(_VerticalJump)
Locked jump	From a standing position, Jump as high as possible without first bending your knees	2	(_VerticalLockJump)

Table 3.3: Jumps.

3.4.3 Isometric hip strength assessment

Testing of hip muscles is performed using the isometric strength of hip assessment tool (iSHAT) (Figure 3.1). Adjust the load cell strap assembly so that the cuff attached to the load cell can be positioned above the knee.

Figure 3.1: The isometric strength of hip assessment tool (iSHAT).

Test	Position	Ask the participant to...	Rest	Number of repetitions	Trial name
Hip Flexion	With knee bent	Flex the hip	2 mins	2	(_HipFlex)
Hip Extension	With knee straight	Extend the hip	2 mins	2	(_HipExt)
Hip Abduction	With knee straight	Abduct the hip	2 mins	2	(_HipAbd)
Hip Adduction	With knee straight	Adduct the hip	2 mins	2	(_HipAdd)

Table 3.4: Isometric hip strength protocol.

4 Strength testing (Biodex dynamometry)

4.1 Adjust the participant position

- 👉 Participant sits braced against adjustable backrest in ~90 degrees hip flexion
- 👉 Knee level with centre of rotation of biodex arm
- 👉 Width of hand between chair and popliteal fossa/back of the shank of flexed knee
- 👉 Attach dynamometer arm
- 👉 Strap participant across chest and hips and above knee
- 👉 Set towards and away limits on Biodex
- 👉 Advise participant of safety button
- 👉 Minimum 1-minute rest between similar contractions

Sit the participant in the chair of the BIODEX dynamometer. Adjust the height and position of the chair until the knee is level with the dynamometer centre of rotation (Figure 4.1). You should be able to place your hand between the edge of the chair and the back of the participant's leg (Figure 4.2). Fasten the chest and waist straps so that they are firm, but not uncomfortable. Place the strap over the participant's knee and fasten firmly.

Figure 4.1: The Biodex dynamometer (without attachments) showing the knee centre of rotation positioned in line with the dynamometer centre of rotation.

Attach the knee attachment to the Biodex and tighten the screw. Show the participant where the emergency stop button is and explain that if they feel pain or discomfort at any time that they should press the button. Set the 'toward' and 'away' limits on the set up tab (Figure 4.3). Positioning the participant in maximum knee flexion and clicking 'Set toward limit', then ask the participant to completely extend their knee and click 'Set away limit'.

Figure 4.2: Positioning of the knee relative to the seat, you should be able to place your hand between the seat and participants leg.

Figure 4.3: The set up tab of the LabView software.

4.2 Familiarisation and warm up

It is important to familiarise the participant to the Biodex to prevent injury and obtain the best results. Before each of the tests below, allow the participant to become familiar with the Biodex and required movement and to warm up before strength tests. Allow the participant one to two minutes to get used to the sensation of the passive movement and isokinetic tests before data acquisition. Before isometric and isokinetic strength tests allow the participant to warm up at 60% of voluntary max effort for 3-4 trials but as many trials as required.

4.3 Passive strength test

- Make sure that you have set towards and away limits on Biodex
- Advise participant of safety button

Task: Passive Trial @ 60°/s

Repetitions: 1

Additional equipment: nil

File name: «partid»_Passive

4.4 Isometric strength test

Tasks: Four (4 repetitions each)

Setup: Adjust Biodex arm to 60° or 30° of knee flexion according to test. Remember to lock in position.

Instructions to participants:

1) Ramp up to maximum knee extension (i.e., kicking a soccer ball) and hold for 3 seconds

2) You will then rest that muscle group while you perform maximum knee flexion (i.e., pulling your foot back)

NB: Minimum 1-minute rest between similar contractions.

Initial set up: Move Biodex arm to 60° of knee flexion. Lock arm in position.

For the first task there are no instruction for the foot position. The participant contracts as they wish, according to the above instructions.

Knee Extension w/ knee @ 60°

Repetitions: 4

Additional equipment: nil

File name: «partid»_IM_Quads

For the second task ask the participants to point their toes to isolate the muscles of the thigh.

Knee Extension with pointed toe w/ knee @ 60° Repetitions: 4

Additional equipment: nil

File name: «partid»_IM_Gastrocs

Adjust set up: Move Biodex arm to 30° of knee flexion. Lock arm in position.

For the third task there are no instruction for the foot position. The participant contracts as they wish, according to the above instructions to participants.

Knee Flexion w/ knee @ 30°
File name: «partid»_IM_Hams

Repetitions: 4

Additional equipment: nil

For the fourth task ask the participants to flex the knee, pulling towards the midline. This is to isolate the Gracilis.

Knee Flexion towards midline w/ knee @ 30°
File name: «partid»_IM_Gracilis

Additional equipment: nil

4.5 Isokinetic strength test

Tasks: Three

Set up: Unlock Biodex arm, remind participant of the safety button, double check that you have set toward and away limits and set speed according to the following tasks.

Instructions to participants: The Biodex will start to move at speed that I set. Initially we will start slow and then do a faster task. When I tell you to, I want you to contract your muscle to push or pull against the arm of the Biodex.

As the arm moves through the range try to push or pull to make it go faster.

Concentric (with biodex) @ 60°/s
File name: «partid»_IK_Con60)

Repetitions: 1

Additional equipment: nil

As the arm moves down contract to try to make it go faster. Rest as it moves away from you.

Concentric (with biodex) @ 180°/s
File name: «partid»_IK_Con180)

Repetitions: 1

Additional equipment: nil

As the arm moves away from you contract to try to stop it. Rest as it moves back towards you.

Eccentric (against biodex) @ 60°/s
File name: «partid»_IK_Ecc60)

Repetitions: 1

Additional equipment: nil

5 Motion capture

5.1 Marker placement

Place PRMs after EMG tests (link)

Constantly communicate with the participant to tell them what you are doing

Palpate the bony landmark

Mark the landmark with a fine marker pen

Place the PRM

Reinforce the PRM

Reinforce EMG with coband

The standard Griffith University (GU) marker set is a full body marker set that consists of 93 markers. The expanded GU marker set is the same as the standard GU marker set but with 4 additional markers in the thigh and shank clusters of the lower limb (109 markers in total) (Appendix 1). Markers should be affixed to the skin using double sided tape and reinforced using micropore or sports tape. Sports tape is better for markers on shoes, micropore is preferable for securing markers to the skin.

Note that the first task of the motion capture is the barefoot static. Apply markers to the rest of the body and then palpate and mark the bare feet and capture the barefoot trial. Remove the markers from the feet only and get the participant to put on standard shoes (i.e., Dunlop Volleys). Palpate and mark the foot with shoes on. Capture the shod static and remaining dynamic trials.

5.2 Static and calibration trials

Reconstruct trials to make sure that you have all markers

Photos of participant wearing the marker set in the static position

5.2.1 Static Calibration Trials (*_StaticCal*)

Tasks: Two – Barefoot static; shod static.

Set up: Zero force plate before participant steps onto it. Participant stands facing the east wall (beach end) with their left foot on force plate one right foot on force plate two.

Instructions to participants:

- Standing on the force plates facing the East wall with your heels in line with the rear edge of the force plate and your feet parallel with the long edges of the plate
- Lower limbs approximately neutral, i.e. ankle inversion and plantar flexion and knee flexion angles approximately zero
- Shoulders flexed and adducted 45° and forearms pronated (so dorsal hand and forearm markers visible), NOT in the crucifix position

Calibration markers should be removed. For both the Griffith marker set and the expanded Griffith marker set these are the left and right:

Medial and lateral femoral condyles (LFC; MFC)	Medial and lateral malleoli (LMAL, MMAL)
Medial and lateral tibial condyles (LTC, MTC)	Medial and lateral elbow (LEL, MEL)
Inter-metatarsal 2/3 joint space (MET23)	Medial and lateral wrist (LWR, MWR)
Anterior and posterior shoulder (ASH, PSH)	

5.3 Dynamic Trials

Walking

Running

Squatting

Side-step/cutting

Sit to stand

5.3.1 Walking

Tasks: Three (left and right sides) – Normal walk; slow walk; fast walk.

Set up: Walk from western (Olsen ave) end of the lab towards the back wall. Allow the participant as many practice attempts as they need to become familiar with the task and to get their stride right to hit the force plate.

Task: Normal speed walk **Repetitions: 5 (each limb)** **Additional equipment: nil**
File name: «partid»_L/R_NormalWalk

Instructions to participant:

- Walk at your 'normal' speed, the speed that you comfortably walk at
- Walk with your head up and looking straight ahead
- Do not target the force plate

Task: Slow speed walk **Repetitions: 5 (each limb)** **Additional equipment: nil**
File name: «partid»_L/R_SlowWalk

Instructions to participant:

- Walk at 'slow' speed, the speed that you might walk at if you were fiddling with your phone
- Walk with your head up and looking straight ahead
- Do not target the force plate

Task: Fast speed walk **Repetitions: 5 (each limb)** **Additional equipment: nil**
File name: «partid»_L/R_FastWalk

Instructions to participant:

- Walk at 'fast' speed, you need to be somewhere in a hurry

Task: Constrained squats

Repetitions: 5 Additional equipment: Slant Board & Pole

File name: «partid»_ConstrainedSquat

Instructions to participant:

- Constrained squat is meant to ensure upright trunk position
- Main difference is to keep trunk parallel with the pole/partition in front of you. Do not make contact with the pole, and do not arch back/stick out bum etc
- Squat as deeply as possible, pause for three seconds and return to standing
- Descend/ascend at a speed that is comfortable for you
- Keep your feet parallel and shoulder width apart
- Before starting descent, hold arms out front and weight should be maintained evenly between both feet

Additional set up:

- Pole/partition should be placed directly in front of participant, but not on the force plate, to provide visual feedback to not lean forward on decent
- Pole/partition is not to be used for support or knocked over

5.3.4 Side-step cutting

Tasks: One

Set up: Start from West (Olsen ave) end of the lab, running towards the East (Beach) end.

Task: Side-step Cutting

Repetitions: 5 (each limb)

Additional equipment: nil

File name: «partid»_L/R_Cut

Instructions to participant:

- Run as fast as you can or as fast as you are comfortable with and when you get to the force plate cut 45° (towards north wall for right leg, south wall for left leg)
- Run with your head up and looking straight ahead
- Do not target the force plate

5.3.5 Raise from chair

Tasks: one

Set up: Place chair/stool adjacent to long edge of force platforms one and four, facing the Oval (north wall) side. The chair should not be on the plates. Zero force plates.

Start position: Seated with feet off plates. Shoulders abducted to 45° so that all arm and chest markers are visible.

Task: Sit to stand

Repetitions: 2

Additional equipment: back-less chair or stool

File name: «partid»_SitStand

Instructions to participant:

- From the start position, cross your arms across your chest so that each hand is on the opposite shoulder
- Place your feet on the force plates, one foot on each plate and pause for 2 seconds
- Stand up at normal speed, do not use excessive upper body movement to gain momentum

6 References

1. Hermens, H.J., et al., *Development of recommendations for SEMG sensors and sensor placement procedures*. Journal of electromyography and Kinesiology, 2000. **10**(5): p. 361-374.
2. Perotto, A.O., *Anatomical guide for the electromyographer: the limbs and trunk*. 2011: Charles C Thomas Publisher.

Master Dataset Collection Sheet

Date: ___/___/___

Tester: _____

Participant Information:

Subject Code: M_____

Segment lengths and angles

Sex: Female Male

Inter ASIS: _____mm Right leg: _____mm Left leg _____mm

DOB: ___/___/___

Right foot(heel-halux) _____mm Left foot(heel-halux) _____mm

Height: _____mm

Right foot(heel-long toe) _____mm Left foot(heel-long toe) _____mm

Weight: _____kg

Right foot eversion: _____° Left foot eversion: _____°

Study limb: Left Right

Dominant limb: Left Right

(Leg to kick a ball/fall test)

Setup and Vicon Configuration:

Before participant arrives:

Tape markers (74 markers, 10 clusters):

Create camera masks:

Calibrate cameras (< 0.2 error):

Set origin:

Create subject from template:

Check capture rates:

Analog capture rate 2000 Hz: Yes No

Video capture rate: 200 Hz: Yes No

EMG equipment

EMG sensors: charged taped:

Razors:

Abrasion pads:

Alcohol swabs:

Biodex

Switched on: Computer: Unit:

Program started:

Attached arm:

EMG Sensors

EMG system used: Cometa Noraxon Other (please specify): _____

EMG Placement

See protocol manual for sensor location and orientation protocol.

The following muscles [sensor number] will be collected:

Anterior thigh

vasmed [1]
 vaslat [2]
 recfem [3]
 gra [4]
 sar [5]
 tfl [14]

Posterior thigh

addmag [8]
 semimem [9]
 bicfemlh [10]
 gmed [15]
 gmax [16]

Shank

tibant [6]
 perlong [7]
 gasmed [11]
 gaslat [12]
 sol [13]

EMG MVIC Tests

While, participant is seated acquire two maximum contractions of each of the following against manual resistance under one file:

Dorsiflexion (_Dorsiflexion) Ankle Eversion (_Eversion) Sartorius #1 (_Sartorius1)

With subject standing and against manual resistance acquire two maximum contractions of each of the following:

Hip Flexion (_HipFlex) Hip Abduction (_HipAbd)
 Hip Extension (_HipExt) Hip Adduction (_HipAdd)

Additionally, acquire two trials of the following:

Vertical Jump (CMJ) (_VerticalJump) Jump (Locked) (_VerticalLockJump)

Strength testing (Biodex Dynamometry):

Set up participant in Biodex according to protocol, strap them in and set towards and away limit

Passive

Passive Trial @ 60°/s (_Passive)

Isokinetic

Concentric (withBiodex) @ 60° s⁻¹ x 1 rep of 5 cycles (_IK_Con60)
 Concentric (with Biodex) @ 180° s⁻¹ x 1 rep of 5 cycles (_IK_Con180)
 Eccentric (against Biodex) @ 60° s⁻¹ x 1 rep of 5 cycles (_IK_Ecc60)

Isometric

Knee Extension w/ knee @ 60° (of flexion) x 4 reps (_IM_Quads)
 Knee Extension (pointed toes) w/ knee @ 60° (of flexion) x 4 reps (_IM_Gastrocs)
 Knee Flexion w/ knee @ 30° (of flexion) x 4 reps (_IM_Hams)
 Knee Flexion towards midline w/ knee @ 30° (of flexion) x 5 reps (_IM_Gracilis)

Marker Placement and calibration

Use GU 10 marker cluster set where possible or GU 6 marker cluster set.

Palpate, mark, double check bony landmarks and place markers. See manual for marker locations

Static and calibration trials

Barefoot static (_BarefootStaticCal) **Static Calibration Trial** (_StaticCal)

NOT in the crucifix position. In the anatomical position, heels in line with the rear (Olsen Ave) edge of the plate, lower limbs approximately neutral hip rotation

Reconstruct and label model to check all markers visible

Photos of marker set

Digital photos of marker set for anthropomorphic scaling of the model taken in the static position

From the front (coronal plane) from the shoulders down

From the feet from about 45° posterolateral

From the legs (waist down) in the frontal plane

From the back (coronal plane) from the shoulders down

Functional Joint Centre Trial **1 repetition** _OPJC

Hip hemisphere star movement 1 second each movement (hip)

Knee same as squats 1, 2,1 @ 90°

Dynamic Trials

Walking

Normal speed walk **Repetitions: 5 (each limb)** **Additional equipment: nil**
File name: «partid»_L/R_NormalWalk

Notes:

Slow speed walk **Repetitions: 5 (each limb)** **Additional equipment: nil**
File name: «partid»_L/R_SlowWalk

Notes:

Fast speed walk **Repetitions: 5 (each limb)** **Additional equipment: nil**
File name: «partid»_L/R_FastWalk

Notes:

Running

Slow Run (3.5 ms⁻¹)

Repetitions: 5 (each limb)

Additional equipment: nil

File name: «partid»_L/R_SlowRun

Notes:

Fast Run (4.5 ms⁻¹)

Repetitions: 5 (each limb)

Additional equipment: nil

File name: «partid»_L/R_FastRun

Notes:

Squats

Instructions to participant:

- Place slant board on force plates and zero force plates
- Squats are to be performed with one foot on each plate, facing towards workstation
- Capture a good second before descent
- Decent and ascent at self-selected pace, **3 second hold**. vicon operator to count aloud

Squats (unconstrained)

Repetitions: 5

Additional equipment: Slant board

File name: «partid»_Squat

Notes:

Constrained squats

Repetitions: 5

Additional equipment: Slant board & pole

File name: «partid»_ConstrainedSquat

Notes:

Side-step Cutting

Instructions to participant:

- Run as fast as you can or as fast as you are comfortable with and when you get to the force plate cut 45° (towards north wall for right leg, south wall for left leg)
- Run with your head up and looking straight ahead
- Don't target the force plate

Side-step Cutting

Repetitions: 5 (each limb)

Additional equipment: nil

File name: «partid»_L/R_Cut

Notes:

Raise from chair

Instructions to participant:

- From the start position, cross your arms across your chest so that each hand is on the opposite shoulder
- Stand up at normal speed

Start position is seated with shoulders abducted to 45° so that all arm and chest markers are visible. Arms then cross the chest so that each hand is on the opposite shoulder.

Task: Sit to stand

Repetitions: 5

Additional equipment: back-less chair or stool

File name: «partid»_SitStand

Notes: